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PUBLICATION OF THE PATENT OFFICE

INTRODUCTION

In view of the recent amendment made in the Patents Act, 1970 by the Patents (Amendment) Act, 2005 effective from 01st January 2005, the Official Journal of The Patent Office is required to be published under the Statute. This Journal is being published on weekly basis on every Friday covering the various proceedings on Patents as required according to the provision of Section 145 of the Patents Act 1970. All the enquiries on this Official Journal and other information as required by the public should be addressed to the Controller General of Patents, Designs & Trade Marks. Suggestions and comments are requested from all quarters so that the content can be enriched.

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21st OCTOBER, 2022

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(54) Title of the invention : DESIGNING A SMART SYSTEM EMBEDDED WITH BIOSENSORS FOR ISOLATION AND IDENTIFICATION OF BACTERIA FROM FRUITS AND VEGETABLES

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(57) Abstract :
 Designing a Smart System Embedded with Biosensors for Isolation and Identification of Bacteria from Fruits and Vegetables is the proposed invention. The invention aims at analysing the bacteria that is found in fruits and vegetables. The proposed invention includes plurality of bio sensors that are embedded in the framework for identifying the quality of fruits and vegetables to bring in the practice of hygiene.

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